

Retailers' satisfaction towards Mall Management for positive Shoppers' perception

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Abstract

The present study explores the effects of the retailers' preference for malls and its impact on customers' perception in India. Growth in organized retail formats in India has been boosted by the liberalization policies pursued by the government. The transformation in the retail landscape is apparent, as malls are being set-up across the country. The purpose was to understand the retailers' reasons for selecting a mall, and the predictors to their satisfaction with a mall towards improving patronage in the shoppers. The social association that the consumer relates to the experience of shopping depends on the environment of the store. Research has given priority to customers' perception and behaviour towards malls. There is little research from the retailers' perspective. This paper explores retailers' satisfaction towards malls. Developing a store image that is culturally significant for the shopper will help form the retailer's image and reputation. The questionnaire was administered on mall retailers. Our focus was retailers having outlets in malls in Hyderabad and Secunderabad. Retailers were asked to complete a structured questionnaire in which they had to indicate their agreement on a 5-point Likert type scale (1 – strongly disagree, 5 – strongly agree). A questionnaire based on a five-item Likert scale, as well as Systematic sampling, was employed for data collection. Data analysis was accomplished using SPSS software. The results show that the correlation is positive between retailer satisfaction and mall management. There was no positive relationship of entertainment and ambience of the malls with retailers' satisfaction towards malls. The results suggest that Indian retailers give more emphasis to efficient space allocation, layout management and promotional endeavours taken up by mall owners while selecting a mall. The availability of services, marketing and professional management of malls is considered imperative by mall retailers. Retailers' satisfaction with malls is affected by efficient mall management and can be increased by professional mall management, arrangement of stores, promotional activities and inclusion of anchor stores.

Keywords: Indian malls; retailers; ambience; entertainment; mall operators store atmosphere, service

Introduction:

India is the fifth largest preferred retail destination globally. The country is among the highest in the world in terms of per capita retail store availability. India's retail sector is experiencing exponential growth, with retail development taking place not just in major cities and metros, but also in Tier-II and Tier-III cities. The Indian retail industry is one of the fastest growing in the world. Retail industry in India is expected to grow to US\$ 1.3 trillion by 2020, registering a Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) of 16.7 per cent over 2015-20. Healthy economic growth, changing demographic profile, increasing disposable incomes, urbanisation, changing consumer tastes and preferences are the other factors driving growth in the organised retail market in India¹. Modern organized retailing, which constitutes currently a small segment of Indian retail industry, is expected to grow to 40% of the market in the coming years (Moriarty et al. 2007). Liberalization policies pursued by the Indian government have encouraged investment in retail real estate. The new malls are being constructed in most of the cities across the country. The intensive competition among malls in the major cities of India has raised an important question of their viability and profitability. The apprehension plaguing most mall owners is whether investment in developing malls would enable them to earn profits in the coming years. New companies are acquiring land for establishing malls with state-of-the-art facilities and infrastructure to entice Indian consumers. To get the first-mover advantages and earn lucrative returns, mall investment has become a hot business proposition. The investment in malls is driven by the changing demographics and psychographics of Indian consumers. Mall operators and owners who were initially focused on the metropolitan cities are now expanding in the smaller cities.

¹<https://www.ibef.org/industry/indian-retail-industry-analysis-presentation>

Research suggests that malls play a significant role in consumers' lifestyle (Bloch, Ridgway, and Dawson 1994; Terblanche 1999) and are multi-leisure complexes (Jones and Hillier 2002). Considering the important role malls play in consumers' life, it is imperative for mall managers to design the mall ambience, facilities and services according to these preferences. The marketing and promotional endeavours of the mall are critical for its survival and profitability. Increased competition among malls for mall traffic and sales has led most mall operators to re-evaluate the services they offer to consumers. This goes hand-in-hand with attracting global brands to open stores and combining this with pleasure and entertainment. Kirkup and Rafiq (1994) state that competition between shopping centres affects getting the best brands to open stores in the malls.

Howard (2007) in her research on leisure shopping in malls suggests that mall owners should understand the complex nature of leisure and accordingly provide facilities to augment it. Retailers are attracted to malls because of efficient facilities, state-of-the-art infrastructure, mall traffic and profits. The mall ambience and infrastructure give the retailer locational competitive advantage. Owning a store space amidst major global brands not only enhances their image but also gets customers. The shopping centre cut 'magnet' stores (Brown 1993) that generate more traffic and indirectly facilitate other retailers to do more business. Thus, the analysis of productivity of malls is an important aspect of retailing (Barros and Alves 2004). The growth of malls has propelled the expansion of high street stores to malls.

Retailers envisage huge profit and product sales in malls and are disposed to pay high rentals for store space in malls. This research on mall retailers endeavoured to understand the factors that play a critical role in generating consumer traffic and boosting sales. The purpose was to understand the retailers' reasons for selecting a mall, and the predictors to their satisfaction with a mall.

This paper consists of the literature review, followed by a section on methodology and data collection. The third section deals with the findings and discussion. The fourth section comprises marketing implications for mall owners, followed by limitations and future research directions.

Literature review

With the growth of the malls industry, where various new malls were built and millions of square feet of retail space were added to existing shopping malls each year (Berman and Evans, 2004), many academic studies were carried out to cover different aspects of shopping malls. The relationship between the malls managers and tenants was one of the addressed aspects (Kirkup and Rafiq, 1994; Prendergast et al., 1996, 1998; Bruwer, 1997; Addae-Dapaah and Yeo, 1999). Research on shopping malls was developed to compare between the views of mall and non-mall retailers (Prendergast et al., 1998). The relationship between malls attributes and productivity was also investigated (LeHew and Fairhurst, 2000). Patronage motives were among the most heavily examined topics in retailing (Yavas, 2003). However, just a few empirical studies have analysed the motivational aspects of consumers that explain their attraction to shopping malls (e.g. Bodkin and Lord, 1997; Ruiz, 1999; Dennis et al., 2001; Nicholls, et al., 2000, 2002). The starting point was that some shoppers were attracted to malls due to purely economic motives; others were attracted due to emotional motives, while multi-purpose shoppers had a combination of these motives (Ruiz, 1999). For example, Bodkin and Lord (1997) concluded that the most important reasons for selecting malls were convenience, presence of a specific store in the mall, services and prices. Nicholls et al. (2000) found that Chilean consumers' mall visits were driven, primarily, by purchasing factors while consumers in the USA visited their mall for more diverse reasons, largely revolving around entertainment. Bloch et al. (1994) examined the effect of mall physical environment on consumers' emotional states and found that malls were viewed by consumers as a place not only for shopping, but also for other activities, such as entertainment. In the same line, Nicholls et al. (2002) found that today's mall patrons tend to be more leisure driven than shoppers in the early 1990s. Wakefield and Baker (1998) found that the mall environment influences the desire to stay and re-patronage intentions to the mall. Other studies have pointed out the importance of the shopping centre image as a critical determinant of consumer patronage decisions (Finn and Louviere, 1996; Sit et al., 2003). Terblanche (1999) studied the impact of four dimensions on shopping centre patronage, namely, functional, recreational, socializing, and convenience. These were based on the perceived benefits that consumers enjoy when visiting a super-regional shopping centre. He found that recreation appears to be the major benefit pursued by shoppers that patronise a super-regional shopping centre. Demographic and psychographic characteristics of mall patrons were also described (Bellenger et al., 1977; Bloch et al., 1994; Roy, 1994). Martin and Turley (2004) studied the attitudes of the young segment (19-25 years old) towards malls, and factors motivating consumption. They found that they were more likely to be objectively Shopping malls attractiveness 937 rather than socially motivated to patronise. In addition to the effect of malls' internal attributes on patronage, other attributes such as travel components that include comfort, reliability of transport mode, effort, tension, distance, and value were significant in affecting shopping centres' patronage (Ibrahim, 2002).

Mall facilities Management

The literature review illustrates the need for Key Performance Indicators that allow analysts to assess the performance of buildings and that also can be used in facilities management and maintenance. As per Brackertz, N (2006) a set of KPIs must be identified and followed over a period so that it can be compared against a baseline in order to scrutinise improvements or

deterioration². Current measurement practices must emphasize aspects like business, business goals, and job satisfaction. Lavy, S., Garcia, J. A., & Dixit, M. K. (2010) stated the traditional metrics relating to financial and space aspects express the performance level of the building but do not indicate the contribution made to the organization's strategic results.³ Mall management implies positioning a mall, attracting the best tenants, formulating tenant mix policies, promotions and facility management (Jones Lang Lasalle Meghraj 2007). The influx of malls in India, as centres of social activity, has a profound impact on retailing. Retailers vie for acquiring space in malls in the hope that the ambience and facilities of the malls give them a competitive advantage to their wares. Designing malls according to consumers' preferences may be instrumental in drawing consumers to the malls and enhancing the overall retail setting (Castaldo and Botti 2001). Mall owners need to organize the malls to attract retailers and help them to earn profits. Sanghvi (2007) suggests that Indian retailer shave focused on understanding the supply-side efficiencies but must rethink more about the demands of the market.

The operation and management of a shopping centre is vital to its success and is an intensive process, which is usually conducted by a multifunctional team, to cover areas of management, marketing, landscaping, maintenance, security and so on. One of the most important management functions is to optimize the return on investment, focusing on strategies that minimize operating costs, including property management, management of operations and facilities. Mall Maintenance plays a significant role in the property management. Maintenance is a necessary part of the retail business. The maintenance management systems should ensure that the mall operates efficiently to preserve and improve the owner's investment. Maintenance in the SC business is more than just repair equipment, and/or systems. It needs to assure the future of the asset for the mall, through a maintenance program that includes activities necessary to maintain the physical infrastructure and the support services. This kind of management is important to ensure the quality and effectiveness of maintenance of facilities that usually vary in their size and type of construction. According to Cable, J.H. and Davis, J.S. (2004) an adequate facility management can result in a support aligned with the organization's mission, the anticipation of future facility requirements, the ability to foresee results of current management decisions, and the reducing of the operational inefficiencies.⁴ The customers' preference for malls depends upon discount schemes, convenience, signage for locating products and sales assistance (De Juan 2004; Miranda et al. 2005). To make shopping devoid of negative aspects of traffic congestion, parking hassles and security concerns (Bloch, Ridgway, and Dawson 1994; Roulac 1994; Erkip 2003), mall owners should design their malls accordingly. Mall managers initiate public relations building promotional activities for attracting consumers to the stores and thereby contributing to profits and sales (Kirkup and Rafiq 1999). Research posits that promotional activities encourage mall visits (Folkes and Wheat 1995; Smith and Sinha 2000; Parsons and Ballantine 2004) and help in giving them a competitive advantage. Conventionally, the focus of mall managers was on promotional activities to draw consumers to the stores (Cardona 2003; Parsons 2003; Parsons and Ballantine 2004), but it also includes generating sales. The malls promotional activities combine both product and service benefits (Castaldo and Premazzi 2001).

Mall management entails attracting top-notch companies and global brands to open stores in the malls. This has a dual advantage; not only do these stores become major traffic attractors but also enable other stores in the malls to earn sales. The mall owners attempt to lease space to popular brands and restaurants. Kirkup and Rafiq (1994) state that the tenants' occupancy in mall affects the consumers' behaviour in shopping in the mall. The malls offering a range of stores such as department stores, apparel stores and entertainment and leisure facilities (Abratt, Fourie, and Pitt 1985; McGoldrick and Thompson 1992; Prendergast, Marr, and Jarratt 1998) do lucrative business.

Mall Atmospherics, Ambience and Services

Previous mall research (e.g., Bellenger, Greenberg and Robertson, 1977; Brown, 1991; Finn, McQuitty and Rigby, 1994; McGoldrick and Thompson, 1992) has reported the impact of mall atmospherics on behavioural responses, but has not examined the role of emotion in determining these behavioural responses. Because there are limited empirical studies on malls, marketing scholars have suggested a need for more research on consumer response to malls (e.g., Bloch, Ridgway and Dawson, 1994; McGoldrick and Thompson, 1992). Several store level studies have examined the effect of a single environmental element, such as music (Yalch and Spangenberg, 1990), colour (Bellizi and Hite, 1992) and accent (Spangenberg, Crowley and Henderson, 1996) on consumer emotion, but there are few studies that examine the effects of multiple environmental elements (cf. Baker, et al., 1992). Everett, Pieters and Titus (1994) aver that relatively little is known about the effects of the global configurations of aspects of the environment. Various factors may be considered vital for mall profitability. Mall attractiveness is affected by consumers' perception about utility and value of retail locations (Fotheringham and O'Kelly 1989).

²Brackertz, N.: Relating physical and service performance in local government community facilities, *Facilities*, Vol. 24 Nos 7/8, pp. 280-91, 2006.

³Lavy, S., Garcia, J. A., & Dixit, M. K.: Establishment of KPIs for facility performance measurement: review of literature. *Facilities*, 28(9/10), 440-464, 2010.

⁴Cable, J.H. and Davis, J.S.: Key Performance Indicators for Federal Facilities Portfolios, Federal Facilities Council Technical Report 147, National Academies Press, Washington, DC, 2004

Tangible and intangible attributes like variety and number of stores, design and parking facilities (Bearden 1977; Castaldo and Botti 2001; Yan and Eckman 2009) motivate consumers to shop in the malls. Research states that a variety of factors affects the success of malls; related to the location of malls (Ownbey, Davis, and Sundel 1994), store atmospherics (Babin and Attaway 2000), size and services and facilities (Downs 1970; Lumpkin, Hawes, and Darden 1986; Brown 1999; Castaldo and Botti 2001; Coye 2004; Keng et al. 2007).

The atmosphere of the store combines affective (emotional or psychological) and cognitive elements (Jackson and Konell 1993). The ambience factors in the malls comprise store layout, interiors, colour, lighting, aisle, heating, store size, crowds, music and cleanliness (Donovan and Rossiter 1982; Donovan et al. 1994) and affect consumers' moods and attitudes thus influencing their purchase intentions (Gardner 1985). Most mall managers realize that mall ambience and attractiveness is a prominent contributor attracting shoppers to stores (Laroche et al. 2005; Michonet et al. 2008) and plays a significant role in consumers' evaluations about products (Baker et al. 1994). Successful retailing must provide interactive environments where the service aspects should be blended (Mathwick, Malhotra, and Rigdon 2001) with the physical ambience (Holbrook 1994). The availability of these facilities has a direct impact on sales and business of malls. Retailers' reasons for preferring malls are associated with a positive ambience, parking facilities, escalators, security and lighting arrangements. The retailer should be willing to pay a higher price for a store space in a mall that is well organized and has good ambience.

Entertainment facilities

The experiential value, or entertainment aspect of retailing, or 'entertaining', is increasingly being recognized as a key competitive tool that responds to threats like internet shopping (Arnold and Reynolds, 2003). Since experience is something personal, it is hard to define. In this study, it is used as a measure for the attractiveness of a shopping area based on interpretations and feelings provoked by the environment in relation with the consumer's motivational orientation. A high experiential value leads to a positive shopping experience and the appreciation of the environment contributes to this experiential value. This study assumes that a positive appreciated aspect leads to a positive effect on the experiential value.

Wakefield and Baker (1998) suggest that a variety of shops in a mall generates positive emotions and excitement. Malls represent a lifestyle and encourage consumers to relax (Guidry and Montero 2005). The impression of the mall is based upon the entertainment facilities, 'a combination of tangible or functional factors and intangible or psychological factors. Malls, due to their architectural design, and 'synergies among retailing, eating and entertaining' (Beyardet et al. 2001; De Nisco and Napolitano 2006) become tourist destinations (Ooi and Sim 2007). The consumers' patronage motives for visiting malls range from seeking variety, entertainment, social interaction, leisure, convenience and relaxation (Haynes and Talpade 1996; Klara 1997; Wakefield and Baker 1998; Kumar and Karande 2000; Michon et al. 2008). Lui (1997) states that malls help consumers lose sense of time as the recreational facilities provide sensory stimulants making them become engrossed in the mall environment. Retailers' preference for malls is affected by availability of variety and entertainment. The 'fun' spaces in the malls are crowd pullers and thus affect sales. The retailer selects a mall if it has food court, gaming area, cinema halls, entertaining activities and promotional programmes to draw customers. The mall traffic leads to more sales and profits. To encourage consumer traffic to the malls, mall owners have to fulfil the consumers' social and hedonic shopping needs (Tauber 1972; Holbrook and Hirschman 1982).

The type of services and stores are responsible for enticing the consumers to the malls. If the malls house major brands, reflects an image of the quality of merchandise (Chebat, Sirgy, and St-James 2006), provides facilities like parking space, food courts, gaming area, sitting area for the elderly and kids and cinema halls, then consumers prefer to frequent the mall. In India, some malls are perceived to be offering novel and the latest wares, coupled with best facilities for parking and eateries. These have become more trendy destinations for mixing shopping with entertainment.

Research Aims and Hypotheses

Despite this fact, there are still unresolved issues concerning the conceptualisation, operationalization and the true nature of the relationship between the two constructs. Nevertheless, for retailers, the problem is how to cope with increased competition taking into account the dynamics of different mall management attributes in order to improve customer satisfaction. To enable informed decisions on this issue, retailers need to know more about the role of each mall management issues such as mall management ambience, mall services and mall entertainment facilities etc. Past studies have also explored how levels of satisfaction varied and retailer perception is differing in relation to basic mall management attributes. It is crucial for retailers to know the magnitude of the relationship between mall management and customer perception towards mall, in their markets, how it is changing, and to be aware of any differences between customer segments. Therefore, the research objective is the investigation of the relationship between mall management attributes and customers perception towards retail format. These objectives led to the formulation of the following research hypotheses

H1₀: Determinant of mall facilities management attributes has no significant relationship on retailer satisfaction in the malls.

H1_a: Determinant of mall facilities management attributes has a significant relationship on retailer satisfaction in the malls.

H2₀: The mall ambience, atmosphere, services have no significant effect on retailer satisfaction in the malls.

H2_a: The mall ambience, atmosphere, services have a significant effect on retailer satisfaction in the malls.

H₃₀: Mall entertainment facilities have no significant effect on retailer satisfaction in the malls.

H_{3a}: Mall entertainment facilities have a significant effect on retailer satisfaction in the malls.

Methodology

The questionnaire was administered on mall retailers, the study focused on retailers having outlets in malls in the twin cities of Hyderabad and Secunderabad. These conjoint metropolitan cities with a population of 7.7 million are economically and commercially more vibrant. Random sampling technique was used. In total, 27 malls were covered and 300 retailers in the malls were contacted. However, we were able to get only 272 complete questionnaires which could be used for the final analysis. Retailers were asked to complete a structured questionnaire in which they had to indicate their agreement on a 5-point Likert type scale (1 – strongly disagree, 5 – strongly agree). The stores in the malls were classified under six categories: food, garments/apparels, electronics, accessories, household items and others. The retailers were asked if they were satisfied by the availability of the facilities in the malls and to list factors that they considered as important for generating sales. The items developed for the questionnaire comprised items related to mall management, ambience/services and entertainment facilities offered at the malls. The total item in the original questionnaire was 27. The items related to malls, related to retailer attitude towards facilities management, ambience, atmosphere, services and entertainment and whether the retailer was satisfied with the mall.

Results and Interpretation

Factor analysis was conducted to reduce the number of attributes to explain the original data to know the mall management attributes / variables which impact the retailer satisfaction for a positive shopper's perception. Factor models were selected based on Kaiser-Meyer- Olkin (KMO) measures of sampling adequacy criteria (should be as near 1 as possible) which is a goodness of fit coefficient, Bartlett's test of sphericity (should be as close to 0 as possible) which is a badness of fit test, the Eigen values greater than 1 and amount of variance explained by the model. Each model was estimated using principal components analysis as the extraction method. Varimax with Kaiser normalization rotation method assisted in interpreting the data for list of value factors activity factors, interest factors, opinion factors and shopping orientation factors. Factors were labelled based on salient loadings. All loadings below 0.5 were dropped, and the factor analysis was recalculated. The Cronbach alpha was used to measure internal reliability by unit weighting items with salient loadings in a factor. Factor Analysis was run on the 27 items related to malls to examine the dimensionality of the scale developed to measure retailers' attitude towards malls and to construct a measurement model. Table 1 represents the results of the Confirmatory Factor Analysis with Varimax rotation and the reliability scores for the scale on the data collected. The analysis revealed three factors that covered 57.64% of variability. Nineteen items were excluded as they had factor loadings of less than 0.6 and failed to meet Nunnally's (1978) recommended level of internal consistency for scale development. These were considered unsuitable for further analysis. The first factor was termed 'mall facilities management' and it includes mall management, organization of space, store layout, marketing of the malls and how professionally malls are managed. The second factor was labeled as 'ambience, atmosphere, services' and it comprised items related to layout of the malls, design, facilities and services which attracted consumers; it had a total of three items. The third factor was labeled 'entertainment facilities' and covered fun space areas in the malls, and consumers preferring malls for entertainment and not shopping; it had two items (Table 1: Factor Analysis). Table 1 shows the factor loadings and Cronbach Alpha values. The Cronbach's alpha for entertainment dimension is 0.589 and is lower than the other two dimensions. The correlation test was administered on the three attributes together with the item 'retailers' were fulfilled with their presence in the malls'. The results are shown in Table 2.

Table 1: Factor loadings of retailer attitudes towards malls attributes.

Construct	Retailer attitude related items	Factor loadings
Mall Facilities Management	➤ Majority of the products have a potential for sale in malls and stores are well organized	0.617
	➤ The malls are in a strategic location for setting up a retail format	0.695
	➤ Mall owner have knowledge and capacity to have a better footfall	0.653
	➤ The customers' find it easy to locate a store in a mall due good layout	0.628
	➤ The malls are workwise organized	0.612
	➤ Cronbach's alpha	0.807
	Mall Atmosphere, Ambience and Services	✓ The central plans of the malls are comforting
✓ The malls cater all category customer		0.637
✓ Restrooms are clean and conveniently located.		0.663
✓ Prompt service at information and delivery desk		0.674

	✓ Cronbach's alpha	0.686
Mall Entertainment Facilities	❖ People come to malls for special and occasional entertainment	0.626
	❖ There are masses of pleasurable and entertaining facilities in the malls	0.696
	❖ Cronbach's alpha	0.562

Table 2: Correlation between retailers fulfilment and mall attributes.

Mall attributes	Retailer fulfilment (satisfaction) with mall attributes.	
Mall Facilities Management	Pearson correlation	0.446
	Sig. (2 tailed)	0.000
	N	272
Mall Atmosphere, Ambience and Services	Pearson correlation	0.067
	Sig. (2 tailed)	0.203
	N	272
Mall Entertainment Facilities	Pearson correlation	0.089
	Sig. (2 tailed)	0.157
	N	272

Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level.

The results show that the correlation is positive between retailer satisfaction and mall management (Pearson correlation = 0.446; $p = 0.000$ and is significant at 0.01 level). This is consistent with earlier research (Brown 1993; Finn and Louviere 1996; Cardona 2003; Konishi and Sandfort 2003; Parsons 2003; Ibrahim and Galven 2007), which states that mall owners should give importance to proper organization of stores, layout and to the marketing activities to attract consumers (Cardona 2003; Parsons 2003; Parsons and Ballantine 2004). The other two attributes, ambience/ service and entertainment facilities, have low correlation (Pearson correlation is 0.067 and 0.089 respectively). The occupant mix and marketing strategies of the malls can help the retailers obtain more mall traffic. The results suggest that Indian retailers give more emphasis to efficient space allocation, layout management and promotional endeavors taken up by mall owners while selecting a mall. The availability of services, marketing and professional management of malls is considered imperative by mall retailers.

There was no positive relationship of entertainment and ambience of the malls with retailers' fulfilment towards malls. This may be attributed to the fact that good ambience, service facilities and variety of stores are considered by retailers' to represent a professionally managed mall. The retailers feel that in a mall they would not have to bother about the facilities as their needs would be dealt by the mall owner. It was the responsibility of the mall owners to provide them with proper support system and facilities for doing business. If they rented a store in street markets, they would have to manage the services for themselves and setting up the infrastructure would entail large investment. The professional set-up of malls was a major attraction for retailers, as the only issue they had to bother about was paying the rent.

To test the above hypothesis, simple linear regression analysis is used to estimate the mediating effect of Mall facility management, Mall atmosphere, ambience, services, and Mall entertainment facilities on the relationship between retailers' satisfaction.

H_{10} : Determinant of mall facilities management attributes has no significant relationship on retailer satisfaction in the malls.

H_{1a} : Determinant of mall facilities management attributes has a significant relationship on retailer satisfaction in the malls.

To test the above hypothesis, simple linear regression analysis is used to estimate the mediating effect of Mall facility management on retailer's satisfaction. The resulting regressing model for retailer's satisfaction with mall management attributes is statistically significant ($F(1,272) = 83.650, p = 0.001$). The regression modal summary results shown in Table 3 indicate that independent variables are related to dependent variable, and predicted by 12.6 percent variation by mall management attributes in retailer satisfaction.

Table 3 Regression modal summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	0.356 ^a	0.126	0.125	1.127	0.126	83.650	1	272	0.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Mall Management Attributes

Source: Primary data

The coefficient summary for evolved regression models shown in Table 4 revealed that mall management attributes ($\beta=0.320$, $t=9.146$, $p=0.005$) had significant influence on retailer satisfaction in malls (retailing organisations). Thus, alternative hypothesis (H_{1a}) is accepted.

Table 4 Coefficient summary for regression model

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t-value	Sig. (p-value)
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.230	0.107		20.826	0.000
	Mall Management Attributes	0.320	0.035	0.356	9.146	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: Retailer satisfaction

Source: Primary data

Results: The results disproved the null hypothesis (H_{10}) and accepted alternative hypothesis (H_{1a}) that the upsurge efficiency of mall management attributes significantly increase the retailers’ satisfaction.

H_{20} : The mall ambience, atmosphere, services have no significant effect on retailer satisfaction in the malls.

H_{2a} : The mall ambience, atmosphere, services have a significant effect on retailer satisfaction in the malls.

To test the above hypothesis, simple linear regression analysis is used to estimate the influence of Mall ambience, services on retailers’ satisfaction in malls. The resulting regressing model for retailers’ satisfaction with mall ambience & services is statistically significant ($F(1,272) = 158.608$, $p=0.001$). The regression modal summary results shown in Table 5 indicate that independent variables are related to dependent variable, and predicted by 21.3 percent variation by mall ambience & services in retailers’ satisfaction strategies.

Table 5 Regression modal summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.464 ^a	.215	.214	.399	.215	158.608	1	272	.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Mall ambience & services elements

Source: Primary data

The coefficient summary for evolved regression models shown in Table 6 revealed that Mall ambience & Service elements ($\beta=0.169$, $t=12.594$, $p=0.0015$) had significant influence on retailers’ satisfaction in malls (retailing organisations).

Table 6 Coefficient summary for regression model

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig. (p-value)
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.352	0.051		26.547	0.000
	Mall ambience, atmosphere, services	0.169	0.013	0.464	12.594	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: Retailers’ satisfaction

Source: Primary data

Results: The results failed to accept null hypothesis (H_{20}). The alternative hypothesis (H_{2a}) is proved to be accepted that the increase, placement of mall ambience & service have significantly increase retailers’ satisfaction in malls.

H_{30} : Mall entertainment facilities have no significant effect on retailer satisfaction in the malls.

H_{3a} : Mall entertainment facilities have a significant effect on retailer satisfaction in the malls.

To test the above hypothesis, simple linear regression analysis is used to estimate the influence of Mall entertainment facilities on retailers’ satisfaction in malls. The resulting regressing model for retailers’ satisfaction with Mall entertainment facilities is statistically significant ($F(1,272) = 238.681, p=0.001$). The regression modal summary results shown in Table 7 indicate that independent variables are related to dependent variable, and predicted by 19.4 percent variation by Mall entertainment facilities in retailers’ satisfaction strategies.

Table 7 Regression modal summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	0.696 ^a	0.485	0.484	0.796	.194	238.681	1	272	0.000

a. Predictors: (Constant), Mall ambience & services

Source: Primary data

The coefficient summary for evolved regression models shown in Table 8 revealed that Mall entertainment facilities ($\beta=0.661, t=23.330, p=0.0015$) had significant influence on retailers’ satisfaction in malls (retailing organisations).

Table 8 Coefficient summary for regression model

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig. (p-value)
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.479	0.095		15.514	0.000
	Mall entertainment facilities	0.661	0.028	0.696	23.330	0.000

a. Dependent Variable: Retailers’ satisfaction

Results: The results failed to accept null hypothesis (H_{30}). The alternative hypothesis (H_{3a}) is proved to be accepted that the increase, placement of Mall entertainment facilities elements have significantly increase retailers’ satisfaction in malls.

Discussion of results

Theoretically, the outcome of this research provides empirical evidences for the influence of selected mall attributes on retailers satisfaction. The study contributes to the retail marketing literature providing empirical considerations when using dynamic mall management attributes towards retailers satisfaction. The empirical findings also provide comprehensive understand about mall management and retailers satisfaction in the context of Indian retailing. Retailers observing for space in Indian malls are worried about their profitability, as high rentals and limited clientele pose a threat to the survival of the store. The retailers look for the malls that attract many consumers and are devoid of negative components that discourage customers from visiting them. Retailers’ choice for opening a store in the malls is dependent on the mall management’s ability to attract consumers. Retailers’ perceptions regarding productivity of the mall are significant in inspiring them to open stores. From the retailers perspective, the malls that convey ‘suitable ambience’ with variety of products and ‘anchor stores’ are considered profitable business venues. Markin, Lillis, and Narayana (1976) suggested that environmental cues permeate the retail environment; our research also has similar implications. Retailers expect the mall management to endow the malls with relevant cues in the form of stores of branded apparel, cinema halls, dining area and recreational centres for drawing consumers to the malls.

The mall absences are emotional or intangible elements in shopping centre directly affects its performance. While planning the store, merchandize layout, design and ambience of malls, restrooms, site outs, space should be allocated to promote diversity in assortment, so that consumer has varied options at one place. Parsons and Ballantine (2004) stated that “promotional activities would also improve the performance and pull consumers to the shopping centres. Retailers were of the view that if consumers visited the mall for watching a film or just for spending time, there is a probability that they would also shop. The shopping centres should provide parking facilities, easy accessibility, elevators, clean ambience with lot of space for walking, spacious dining areas and recreational facilities”. The mall managers should take steps to ensure that the malls communicate the appropriate image in the minds of not only the consumers but also the retailers. This would enable the malls to battle against competition and help them to charge a high rent from the retailers for store space. Retailers are willing to pay a high rent for acquiring space in malls that can generate more consumer traffic.

Mall management in India should look forward to positioning their malls to attract consumers finally they may entice retailers. So far, all the malls are perceived to be similar with no differentiation in the anchor stores and layouts. New malls will have to look at the under-penetrated areas for planning their location. Existing malls should work upon establishing an identity for themselves by differentiating on entertainment and services. The high rentals in the malls should be used for mall promotions. Community programmes to connect with the local community may play a significant role in mall branding. At

present, mall management is focused towards only earning profits for the owners and there is no effort to market the mall. It is vital that the mall management and the occupants should cooperate with each other and develop strategies to encourage consumer visits to the malls. This would heighten the emotional experience of the consumers in the malls and attract visitors to the mall. The high rentals of the mall become viable if mall management broaden their view of mall management and look beyond improving the ambience and entertainment facilities. These two are hygiene factors for keeping the mall operational; however, the current level of competition requires a holistic approach towards mall management.

Directions for future research

This study has not explored critical factors affecting retailers profitability, merchandize assortments (potentiality), local consumer requirements, competition at the mall level. Though it is a common phenomenon to consumer patronage multiple stores in an evolving retail market, yet it need to be investigated. There is very little research to examine the retailers' perspective and preference for mall space. The profitability of malls is dependent upon the best branded stores coupled with modern facilities. Thus, the mall owners should focus on attracting the brands that are popular among consumers, as it would help them in earning profits, research to be done on the elements which impact on the retailers profitability. Retailers are attracted to malls because of the structured, organized and flamboyant ambience. The earlier research has discussed issues about efficient services (Cardona 2003; Parsons 2003; Parsons and Ballantine 2004) and anchor stores (Finn and Louviere 1996; Konishi and Sandfort 2003; Ibrahim and Galven 2007) in malls for attracting consumers. We believe that research should be undertaken from the perspective of retailers in selecting malls. The retailer's attitude towards malls is as significant as the consumers' reasons for visiting malls. The issue of mall management can be a pivotal issue for attracting consumers and retaining good retailers in malls. Location and marketing of the malls with respect to the demographic profile of the nearby communities is an interesting research area. There needs to be research to understand the costs associated with the malls to plan efficient allocation of funds for improving the profitability of the malls. Research on consumers' behaviour in terms of size, store mix, convenience and their expenditure behaviour in India could help promoters design new mall projects.

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